

PROTECTION OF MASONRY STRUCTURES AGAINST EXPLOSIONS APPLYING LAYERS OF TEXTILE REINFORCED MORTAR

Leonidas A. Kouris¹, Georgios Valsamos¹, Savvas Triantafyllou², Vasileios Karlos¹, Daniel A. Pohoryles¹, Dionysios A. Bournas¹, Martin Larcher¹ and Folco Casadei¹

¹ European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC)
Via E. Fermi, 2749, I-21027 Ispra (VA), Italy

e-mail: {Leonidas.KOURIS, Georgios.VALSAMOS, Vasileios.KARLOS, Daniel.POHORYLES, Dionysios.BOURNAS, Martin.LARCHER, Folco.CASADEI}@ec.europa.eu

² National University of Athens

Institute for Structural Analysis and Aseismic Research, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, GR-15780, Greece
e-mail: savtri@mail.ntua.gr

Keywords: Textile reinforced mortar, Blast loads, Explicit model, Experimental calibration

Abstract. *The protection of masonry walls against blast-induced loads by using textile-reinforced mortar (TRM) is investigated herein. Typically the consequences to a structure from explosions (either intentional or accidental) may range from total or partial building collapse due to the direct release of energy to injuries and fatalities due to the created debris. Masonry elements are of stiff and brittle nature and demonstrate considerable resistance in medium-sized compressive loads but degrade dramatically for stronger loads and impacts under tensile stresses. TRM constitutes a novel composite, using open-mesh textiles made from fibre rovings, which has been proven effective as strengthening material to carry the tensile stresses of out-of-plane inertial loading, while satisfying the necessary compatibility, reversibility and durability requirements for masonry buildings. Retrofitting of existing structures with the use of TRM can substantially increase their strength and deformation capacity, providing a sufficient protection to the occupants from blast loads. It should be noted that improving the deformation capacity of masonry can increase the gravitational load bearing capacity of the structure and minimise second order phenomena during a blast event. In this work, we propose a numerical method to accurately predict the various structural effects of explosions on masonry. The focus is to evaluate the developed damage due to impulsive loads and investigate the enhancement of the global dynamic response of a masonry wall before and after retrofitting. Masonry consists of brick units surrounded by mortar joints. The brittle behaviour of this two-phase material is modelled in the EUROPLEXUS explicit finite element code for fast transient phenomena, in complex three-dimensional fluid-structure systems. The performance of masonry is described using plasticity laws for the constituent elements and damage for softening. Geometric non-linearity effects accounting for large displacements and large rotations are also considered. The numerical response is validated using out-of-plane experiments of masonry wallets.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Strong blasts and impact loads on structures result in cracking, fracture, diffusion of debris and may lead to their total or partial collapse. The main cause of injuries and fatalities after the impact of a blast wave on a structure is mainly attributed to the impact of the resulting structural fragments and debris on the occupants [1]. While structural integrity cannot be entirely ensured, damage control can be achieved by applying strengthening techniques. A description of the applied loads on structures due to external explosions is available in [2]. However, in the case of large and complex structures, where shadowing and channeling phenomena take place, advanced numerical modelling techniques are required [1,3] to accurately estimate the effect of strengthening on the dynamic response of the structure.

Masonry walls are amongst the most common building components; they can be distinguished in load bearing and non-load bearing elements as in the case of infill walls in reinforced concrete frame buildings. Masonry walls demonstrate a stiff and brittle nature and, even when designed as non-structural elements, they influence to a great extent the structure's response to external or internal explosions. Few studies are available in the literature for simulating textile reinforced mortar (TRM) strengthened masonry structures under seismic loads, and very limited information exists on the modelling of masonry subjected to blast loads and the simulation of the strengthening. The reason of scarce numerical models of TRM strengthened masonry is the presence of four different materials (brick units, mortar, textile, matrix) and their complicated interactions that give rise to numerous and complex damage modes. These necessitate fine resolutions that render numerical simulation a computationally intensive procedure. Therefore, several simplifications need to be performed in order to strike the right balance between the amount of numerical analysis and exhaustive material characterisation tests.

Focusing only on the TRM external layer, the influence of the imperfections of the in-plane position of the textile, i.e., a curved layer of the textile inside the matrix, on its tensile behaviour was studied in [4] using two-dimensional finite element (FE) models. In this, the mortar was simulated using plane stress elements whereas truss elements were used for the textile. As expected, the higher the imperfect and non-straight placement of the textile in the matrix the higher the change of the stiffness of the TRM. To reduce computational costs, reduced order macro-modelling approaches for TRM strengthened masonry walls were presented based on 2D planar models including either a homogenised non-linear (NL) material calibrated to experimental responses [5,6] or different materials for bricks and mortar [7]. The plane elements can overlap and a perfect bond between the masonry, the inorganic basis and, the textile was assumed [8]. In [9], the authors used fully bonded shell elements for the bricks and the mortar and linear elements arranged in a grid for the TRM; the NL material laws were calibrated using experimental data.

Kyriakides et al. [10] performed an experimental campaign and a corresponding numerical investigation studying the out-of-plane and retrofitting of masonry with an external coat made of steel fibres sprayed in a cementitious mortar, the so-called engineered cementitious composite (ECC), with or without a two-dimensional steel textile [11]. The modelling considers brick units and mortar joints separately simulated, whereas a second more simplified approach merges the two materials while maintaining the interfaces between the homogenised elements to simulate the interaction. A perfect bond between the reinforcement and the inorganic matrix is assumed in both models. Moreover, elastoplastic elements are introduced to simulate the interaction between the coat and the masonry.

Unreinforced masonry walls subjected to blast loads have been investigated both experimentally and numerically. A study investigating masonry materials under high strain rate conditions and their influence on the structural behaviour under blast shows that the strain rate effect has

a substantial impact [12]. Large unreinforced masonry walls $2\text{m} \times 2\text{m}$ fixed at their base have undergone blast loads up to collapse and the resulting reflected peak pressures have been determined in [13]. A homogenisation model with strain rate effect has been developed for impact loads on unreinforced masonry walls in [14]. A study concerning masonry loaded by near filed detonations investigated the question of fragmentation of masonry [15]. A review of the available numerical models for masonry structures experiencing blast loads can be found in [16].

In [17–19], the effect of impact loads on masonry stack specimens strengthened with composites has been investigated both experimentally and numerically. The finite element simulation was performed on the basis of an implicit dynamic analysis procedure considering material failure via a smeared cracking model and loss of cohesion at the interfaces. The efficiency of elastomeric materials for strengthening masonry walls against blast loads has been investigated in [20]. The masonry specimens are $\frac{1}{4}$ scaled and made of concrete blocks while the strengthening process involved spraying with a polyurea liner. Single degree of freedom (SDOF) models have been used to simulate masonry performance and estimate their damage producing P-I curves [21].

This study develops a nonlinear FE model in EUROPLEXUS [22], an explicit code, to investigate the strengthening of masonry structural elements using TRM against blast loads.

2 EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

2.1 Test design and set-up

The test campaign conducted in [23], studying the out-of-plane response of masonry piers strengthened with external layers of TRM in the tension side was simulated in the present study. Kariou et al. 2018 [23] tested a series of eighteen specimens in three-point bending as presented in Figure 1, including two control specimens (unstrengthened). The load is increasing monotonically at the mid-span of the masonry piers which have 18 courses of bricks units in a stretcher bond (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Test set-up and dimensions.

Mortar joints were approximately 10 mm thick, and the specimens' dimensions were 1.34 m long $\times$ 0.44 m wide. Wall thickness was a parameter under investigation and therefore, the eight single wythe piers (S) were 0.1025 m thick, while the eight double wythe piers (D) were 0.215 m thick as they include one head mortar joint. Three different fibres were used: (i) carbon (C), (ii) glass (G) and (iii) basalt (B). In this study, only the carbon textile is investigated. Details about the epoxy resin and the impregnation process can be found in [23]. The thickness of the coat is 3 mm for the one-layer carbon textile.

2.2 Material properties

The masonry walls were built using solid clay bricks 65 mm high and with bed face dimensions 215 $\times$ 102.5 mm and a mortar with a mix ratio of 1:4 (cement: sand) by volume. The mortar used for the matrix of TRM is made of cement mixed with polymers at a ratio 8:1 while the water to material weight ratio was kept at 0.23.

Material	Strength [MPa]	Elastic modulus [GPa]	Thickness [mm]
Masonry	9.7	2.5	102.5/215
Reinforcing mortar (matrix)	6.0	0.8	3.0
Carbon (C)	3800	225	0.097

Table 1. Material properties: elastic modulus (GPa), strength (MPa) and thickness (mm).

The masonry's vertical Elastic modulus and nominal strength are equal to 2.5 GPa and 9.7 MPa, respectively, estimated from the mean of three compression tests of masonry wallettes [24]. The matrix mortar compressive strength was found 6.0 MPa. Three different composite textiles have been used: (i) carbon with a nominal thickness 0.097 mm, glass with a nominal thickness 0.044 mm and basalt (coated textile) with a nominal thickness 0.037 mm. Measured material properties for all materials are provided in Table 1.

2.3 Test results

Masonry walls usually experience two predominant failure modes or a combination of the two: (i) textile failure (TX), or (ii) masonry failure (MR). The textile failure can occur either as fibre breakage (FB), or textile debonding (DB) and slippage (SL). Masonry failure can be either flexural with vertical cracks (FL), shear with diagonal cracks (SD) or shear sliding of the bricks on the mortar joints (SV) due to loss of bonding. In both cases (i.e. fibres and masonry) a combination of the failure modes is possible. The specimens retrofitted with carbon TRM failed in textile slippage (single wythe specimen) and textile rupture (double wythe specimen).

3 NUMERICAL MODELLING FOR BLAST LOADING

Finite element analysis has been performed to verify the quasi-static experimental results and then obtain a qualitative assessment of the performance of the specimen under blast loading. The simulations herein are carried out using the explicit finite element solver EUROPLEXUS [22] jointly developed by the French Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA Saclay) and the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC Ispra). The main application domain of the software is numerical simulation of fast transient phenomena including non-linear effects, such as explosions and impacts in complex three-dimensional fluid structure systems and therefore, suits perfectly for the masonry blast analysis applied here.

3.1 Numerical setup

The numerical model of the masonry wall was discretized by 8-node linear brick elements with reduced integration to avoid locking phenomena. A uniform element size of 1cm was opted for to also resolve the mortar joints, see Figure 2. The TRM layer has been modelled with 4-node shell elements with 6 DOFs per node, 4 integration points in the plane and 5 integration points through the thickness. A similar element size of 1cm has been employed for the TRM layer which is sharing common nodes with the masonry wall in order to take into account the bonding between the two different components. The specimen was constrained along the vertical direction (parallel to the load) at the support locations. For the quasi-static tests the load has been implemented somewhat faster (constant velocity of 0.05m/s), using time scaling which implies that the simulation run during a shorter time interval than the duration of the physical process of the test. Time scaling increases the strain rates in the structure, therefore rate-sensitivity has been deactivated from the constitutive model.

Figure 2. Numerical model of the masonry wall.

3.2 Blast load

An idealized form of a blast pressure-time curve at a certain distance from the detonation point and without intermediate obstacles is presented in Figure 3. The shock wave first reaches the point under consideration at the arrival time t_a (which includes the time of the detonation itself). The pressure reaches its maximum value p_{max} (peak-overpressure) almost instantly and starts decaying until it reaches the ambient pressure p_0 (in most cases the atmospheric pressure) within time t_d , called the positive phase duration. The pressure continues to drop below the ambient pressure reaching its minimum value p_{min} , and then starts to rise again reaching the ambient pressure within time t_n , known as the negative phase duration. The exponential decay of the pressure-time history is represented through the modified Friedlander equation [25], that describes the rate of decrease of the blast pressure values. Depending on the distance of the obstacle from the detonation point and the mass of the explosive charge, the desired parameters (time of arrival, pressure magnitudes, duration and impulses) can be defined using the graphs included in [26].

Figure 3. Idealized form of pressure-time history due to explosion (Friedlander equation [25]).

3.3 Material properties and modelling considerations

The response of a perfectly bonded TRM strengthened masonry is generally assumed to be trilinear [27] as shown in Figure 4, where the three subsequent phases I, II_a and II_b are characterised by the moduli E_1 , $E_2 (=0)$ and E_3 , which can be further simplified to a linear one neglecting the first two phases. However, a complex interaction process between filaments, yarns, the matrix, and the masonry takes place which results in a macroscopic debonding and an uneven stress distribution of the fibres microscopically. To this end an estimation of an ‘effective’ elastic modulus is opted for in this study, calibrated from the experimental results. The definition of the effective strain is as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{eff} = \varepsilon + \varepsilon_{bond} \quad (1)$$

where ε_{bond} is the macroscopic ‘strain’ defined as the ratio of the slip to the length of the roving. The TRM coat is modelled assuming only the textile; to this end, the effect of the matrix is introduced as an initial increased stiffness applying the rule of mixtures to reflect its ‘presence’ prior to cracking and loss of tensile capacity.

Figure 4. Typical trilinear stress-strain curve of TRM and a simplified linear one [28].

The mortar and the bricks exhibit a brittle behaviour, therefore a three-invariant cap model with mixed hardening has been used [29]. It includes strain rate sensitivity and isotropic damage,

and has been successfully employed in previous studies representing concrete structures [30]. For the TRM layer a Von Mises material law has been used, where elasto-plasticity with isotropic hardening is implemented via a radial return algorithm.

Failure was modelled using element erosion (element excluded from the calculation for the remaining period) that is triggered when all the integration points in the respective element reach a critical value related with the constitutive law. For the brittle material law, the volumetric plastic strain has been used as a failure criterion, while the threshold has been defined after appropriate parametric studies. For the TRM, a criterion based upon the principal strains has been engaged. The criterion is active when the hydrostatic stress is positive (traction), while when the hydrostatic stress is negative (compression) failure is inactive.

4 MODEL CALIBRATION AND BLAST ANALYSES

4.1 Calibration of the proposed model

The numerical model and the assumptions described in Section 3 are applied to the masonry single and double wythe specimens of the experimental campaign presented in Section 2 to calibrate the effective material properties. The calibrated material properties for both specimens retrofitted with a carbon TRM layer are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. It is noted that a uniform weight is applied to all materials as the analysis is explicit. Masonry and mortar joints are modelled using a concrete NL material law applying a Drucker-Prager strain threshold [22].

Material	Density [kg/m ³]	Young modulus [GPa]	Poison ratio	Compressive strength [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Volumetric strain threshold
Brick	2000	6	0.3	15	1.5	0.2
Mortar	1800	0.4	0.2	5	0.5	0.1

Table 2. Material parameters for brittle constitutive law.

Density [kg/m ³]	Young modulus [GPa]	Poison ratio [-]	Elastic limit [MPa]	Ultimate stress [MPa]	Ultimate strain [%]
3650	225	0.2	250	1600	1.5

Table 3. Effective material parameters for the carbon TRM layer.

The calibration of the effective material parameters for the carbon textile is shown in Table 3 and the comparison between analytical and experimental results are presented in Figure 5 where an excellent matching is observed. Failure is calibrated with high accuracy in both cases as well as the initial stiffness. A reasonably small variation of the stiffness is observed for the double wythe masonry specimen which can be attributed to local aleatory bonding imperfections.

Figure 5. Comparison between experimental results of single (S_C1) and double wythe (D_C1) masonry and numerical model (EPX).

Moreover, comparing the failure mode and the crack propagation among the experimental specimens and the numerical models show a reasonably accurate coincidence as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Failure mode of experimental specimens and analytical representation.

4.2 Application of blast loading

A hemispherical blast wave produced from a 80 kg TNT charge at a standoff distance of 5m has been considered to impinge the upper surface of the wall. This scenario implies a Hopkinson-Cranz scaled distance of $1.16 \text{ m/kg}^{1/3}$ according to the following Equation:

$$Z = R / \sqrt[3]{W} \quad (2)$$

where R is the standoff distance and W is the charge mass.

The materials comprising the masonry wall behave differently under impulsive loading when compared to static or quasi-static loading, due to the effect of the increased strain-rates. Figure 7 presents the comparison of the masonry wall response under blast loading with and without TRM enhancement. The magenta coloured zones indicate the eroded elements after reaching their maximum limit. More accurate representation of the crack propagation needs finer discretisation, but the current one is sufficient to extract qualitative conclusions.

The additional TRM layer appears to prevent the extensive cracking of the mortar. In fact, the opening of the mortar bed joints in the middle zone due to tensile failure is prevented allowing for an additional masonry arch mechanism to develop which, however, is still far from high plastic strains. This additional arch mechanism appears with a moderate diagonal cracking and a compression zone in the middle mortar head joints. Moreover, this mechanism relieves part of the stress and strain tension at the supports.

Monitoring of the number of the failed elements for each case, reveals that the TRM enhanced wall has 20% less eroded elements that is a clear indication of damage reduction. The TRM is not exfoliated, keeping together the individual components of the wall, a characteristic that can contribute towards the reduction of the potential flying debris and their lethal consequences, and thus, increase substantially the safety of the structure.

Figure 7. Damage states for: (a) unreinforced masonry, and (b) retrofitted masonry with TRM.

5 CONCLUSIONS

- A model for unreinforced masonry and masonry strengthened with TRM has been developed in an explicit FE code.

- The material models of the simulation have been calibrated using static out-of-plane experiments.
- The materials strain rate effect due to the impulsive loading has been estimated from the literature.
- Unreinforced and retrofitted masonry piers using one layer of carbon textile in inorganic cement-based matrix (TRM) have been exposed to blast loads.
- Application of one layer of TRM (using carbon textile in inorganic matrix) can substantially increase the capacity against impact and blast loads.
- Flying debris is expected to be substantially reduced and thus, increase the occupant safety.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

L. Kouris and D. Bournas gratefully acknowledge the Marie Skłodowska-Curie ‘SPEctRUM’ project for carrying out this research (Programme/Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2017; Proposal No: 799593 Individual Fellowship).

REFERENCES

- [1] Giannopoulos G, Larcher M, Casadei F, Solomos G. Risk assessment of the fatality due to explosion in land mass transport infrastructure by fast transient dynamic analysis. *J Hazard Mater* 2010;173:401–8. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2009.08.096.
- [2] Karlos V, Solomos G, Larcher M. Analysis of the blast wave decay coefficient using the Kingery–Bulmash data. *Int J Prot Struct* 2016;7:409–29. doi:10.1177/2041419616659572.
- [3] Valsamos G, Casadei F, Solomos G, Larcher M. Risk assessment of blast events in a transport infrastructure by fluid-structure interaction analysis. *Saf Sci* 2019;118:887–97. doi:10.1016/j.ssci.2019.06.014.
- [4] Bertolesi E, Carozzi FG, Milani G, Poggi C. Numerical modeling of Fabric Reinforce Cementitious Matrix composites (FRCM) in tension. *Constr Build Mater* 2014;70:531–48. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2014.08.006.
- [5] Basili M, Marcari G, Vestroni F. Nonlinear analysis of masonry panels strengthened with textile reinforced mortar. *Eng Struct* 2016;113:245–58. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2015.12.021.
- [6] Wang X, Ghiassi B, Oliveira D V., Lam CC. Modelling the nonlinear behaviour of masonry walls strengthened with textile reinforced mortars. *Eng Struct* 2017;134:11–24. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2016.12.029.
- [7] Lignola GP, Prota A, Manfredi G. Nonlinear Analyses of Tuff Masonry Walls Strengthened with Cementitious Matrix-Grid Composites. *J Compos Constr* 2009;13:243–51. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000007.
- [8] Basili M, Vestroni F, Marcari G. Brick masonry panels strengthened with textile reinforced mortar: experimentation and numerical analysis. *Constr Build Mater* 2019;227. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.117061.
- [9] Parisi F, Lignola GP, Augenti N, Prota A, Manfredi G. Nonlinear Behavior of a Masonry Subassemblage Before and After Strengthening with Inorganic Matrix-Grid Composites. *J Compos Constr* 2011;15:821–32. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000203.

- [10] Kyriakides MAA, Hendriks MANAN, Billington SLL. Simulation of unreinforced masonry beams retrofitted with engineered cementitious composites in flexure. *J Mater Civ Eng* 2012;24:506–15. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0000412.
- [11] Kyriakides MA, Billington SL. Behavior of unreinforced masonry prisms and beams retrofitted with engineered cementitious composites. *Mater Struct Constr* 2014;47. doi:10.1617/s11527-013-0138-x.
- [12] Larcher M, Peroni M, Solomos G, Gebbeken N, Bieber P, Wandelt J, et al. Dynamic Increase Factor of Masonry Materials: Experimental Investigations. *ISIEMS, Int. Symp. Interact. Munitions with Struct.*, Potsdam; Germany: 2013, p. 10.
- [13] Ahmad S, Elahi A, Pervaiz H, Rahman AGA, Barbhuiya S. Experimental study of masonry wall exposed to blast loading. *Mater Constr* 2014;64:e007. doi:10.3989/mc.2014.01513.
- [14] Hao H. Numerical modelling of masonry wall response to blast loads. *Aust J Struct Eng* 2009;10:37–52. doi:10.1080/13287982.2009.11465031.
- [15] Dörr A, Gebbeken N, Larcher M, Steyerer M, Haberacker C. The effect of near-field explosions on masonry. *15th Int. Symp. Interact. Eff. munitions Struct.*, Potsdam, Germany: 2013.
- [16] Badshah E, Naseer A, Ashraf M, Shah F, Akhtar K, Bhatti AQ. Review of Blast Loading Models, Masonry Response, and Mitigation 2017. doi:10.1155/2017/6708341.
- [17] Pourfalah S, Cotsovos DM, Suryanto B. Modelling the out-of-plane behaviour of masonry walls retrofitted with engineered cementitious composites. *Comput Struct* 2018;201:58–79. doi:10.1016/j.compstruc.2018.02.004.
- [18] Pourfalah S, Cotsovos DM. Enhancing the out-of-plane behaviour of unreinforced masonry walls under impact loading through the use of partially bonded layers of engineered cementitious composite. *Int J Prot Struct* 2020;11:209–34. doi:10.1177/2041419619866457.
- [19] Pourfalah S, Cotsovos DM, Suryanto B, Moatamedi M. Out-of-plane behaviour of masonry specimens strengthened with ECC under impact loading. *Eng Struct* 2018;173:1002–18. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.06.078.
- [20] Johnson C, Slawson T, Cummins T, Davis J. Concrete masonry unit walls retrofitted with elastomeric systems for blast loads. 2004.
- [21] Mayrhofer C. Reinforced masonry walls under blast loading. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 44, Pergamon; 2002, p. 1067–80. doi:10.1016/S0020-7403(02)00014-0.
- [22] EUROPLEXUS. Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique & European Commission - JRC. User Manual, 2019:1507. <http://www-epx.cea.fr/>.
- [23] Kariou FA, Triantafyllou SP, Bournas DA, Koutas LN. Out-of-plane response of masonry walls strengthened using textile-mortar system. *Constr Build Mater* 2018;165:769–81. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.01.026.
- [24] EN 1052-1. Methods of test for masonry - Part 1: Determination of compressive strength. *Eur Comm Stand* 1999.
- [25] Baker WE (Wilfred E. Explosion hazards and evaluation. Elsevier Scientific Pub. Co; 1983.

- [26] Kingery CN, Bulmash G. Air blast parameters from TNT spherical air burst and hemispherical surface burst. US Army Ballistic Research Laboratory technical report ARBRL-TR 02555. Maryland: Defence Technology Information Center, Ballistic Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground; 1984.
- [27] Kouris LAS, Triantafyllou TC. Design Methods for Strengthening Masonry Buildings Using Textile-Reinforced Mortar. *J Compos Constr* 2019;23. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000906.
- [28] Kouris LAS, Triantafyllou TC. State-of-the-art on strengthening of masonry structures with textile reinforced mortar (TRM). *Constr Build Mater* 2018. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.08.039.
- [29] Kristoffersen M, Hauge KO, Valsamos G, Børvik T. Blast loading of concrete pipes using spherical centrally placed C-4 charges. *EPJ Web Conf* 2018;183. doi:10.1051/epjconf/201818301057.
- [30] Guilbaud D. Damage plastic model for concrete failure under impulsive loadings XIII International Conference on Computational Plasticity. Fundamentals and Applications. In: Oñate E, Owen DRJ, Peric D, Chiumenti M, editors. XIII Int. Conf. Comput. Plast. Fundam. Appl. COMPLAS XIII , Barcelona, Spain : 2015, p. 1031–1042.